

HISTORIOGRAPHICAL ANALYSIS OF THE UZBEK SSR'S INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS IN THE CULTURAL SPHERE

Kodirov Kh.A.

Master's Student, Faculty of History, National University of Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14715912>

Abstract. *This article discusses the study of the Uzbek SSR's international relations in the cultural sphere during 1950–1991.*

Keywords: *international relations, USSR, Uzbek SSR, international cooperation, culture, public organizations.*

Introduction: International cultural relations play an important role in cooperation between countries. Today, the intensification of problems in the global community has a direct impact on the form and significance of international relations between countries. The terrible consequences of international conflicts and the emergence of mass weapons require a change in the principles and norms of global relations.

We can see that international cultural relations serve as a connecting link between countries and greatly contribute to its strengthening.

At the same time, no foreign policy action can achieve a significant result without effective international cooperation. The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoev emphasized this in his article dedicated to the Samarkand Summit of the Shanghai Cooperation Organization on September 12, 2022: "Effective international cooperation is the most important factor of sustainable, reliable and prosperous development in the world. It is precisely such an approach that is the most accurate, acceptable and effective way to jointly solve the pressing problems of our time, to protect against new threats and social shocks".

International cooperation in the field of culture is not only a creative process, but also a social practice. By studying the history of international relations in the field of culture of the Uzbek SSR in 1950-1991, we can learn about the international political, social, and cultural relations of the USSR at that time, changes in them, and the role of the Uzbek SSR in these relations.

A review of the literature on the history of international relations in the field of culture of the Uzbek SSR was conducted by Sh.M. Abdullaev, Ch.A. Abutalypov, M.A. Bobojojaev, R.M. Bobojojaeva, A.A. Isohojaev, K. Karimov, S. Mirzaev, E.Z. Nuriddinov, M.A. Rakhimov, U.A. Rustamov, A.M. Kasimov, A.T. Sobirov, U.A. Soliyev, I The research of these scholars provides important information about the history of Uzbekistan's international relations, the country's political, social, and cultural role and influence in the foreign policy of the USSR.

The results of the research: During the Soviet period, historians studied the history of international relations in the field of culture of the Uzbek SSR in a narrow way, more precisely, on the example of a specific period or some foreign countries.

For example, scientists Sh.M. Abdullaev, E.Z. Nuriddinov, A.T. Sobirov, R.M. Kholmurodov in their scientific research studies studied Uzbekistan's international relations with socialist countries (German Democratic Republic, Hungarian People's Republic, Czechoslovak Socialist Republic, Polish People's Republic) [1], while R.M. Bobojojaeva, U.A. Soliev, N.U. Tulyaganova, Sh.A. Khayitov, A.R. In his research, Sakhibaev identified public organizations operating in the USSR and the Uzbek SSR that were directly involved in establishing international

relations (the Society for Friendship and Cultural Relations of Uzbekistan with Foreign Countries, the "Vatan" Society) [2], cities that contributed to establishing international cultural relations in Asia, Africa, and America, and established sister cities with cities in Uzbekistan [3], and through the connections between them, he revealed the importance of cultural relations between Uzbekistan and the world community.

During the Soviet period, a number of monographs and literature dedicated to the international cultural relations of the Uzbek SSR were published. These include "International Relations of Soviet Uzbekistan" by I. Tukhtakhojaeva, "Uzbekistan - Arab Eastern and African Countries" by A.A. Isohojaev, "Uzbekistan in the Socialist Community" by K. Karimov, "Soviet Uzbekistan and the Foreign East" by M.A. Babohojaev, "International Relations of Uzbekistan" by Ch.A. Abutalypov, "Soviet Uzbekistan in the International Arena" by U.A. Rustamov [4]. This literature is an important source for illuminating and analyzing the diplomatic and cultural ties of Uzbekistan with foreign countries during the Soviet period, as well as for studying the republic's foreign policy.

However, in this scientific literature of the 50s-90s of the 20th century, much attention was paid to the political and cultural relations of the Uzbek SSR, mainly with the Council for Mutual Economic Assistance, the Warsaw Pact member states, and socialist countries [5]. Also, in the Soviet period, these relations were often described in the historiography of our country in a positive, impartial manner, without criticism, without existing problems and solutions. In some cases, criticism was allowed in cases where the USSR expressed dissatisfaction with the policy of a particular country (for example, China, Yugoslavia, Japan, Albania, the Republic of Korea), but information about such countries was often not published [6].

After gaining independence, a critical and objective assessment of Uzbekistan's international relations during the Soviet period, particularly in the field of culture, was given by scholars such as R.M. Bobohojaeva, U.A. Soliev, Sh.A. Khayitov, and A.R. Sakhibaev. According to the historian U.A. Soliev, the scientific literature of the 1950s-1990s also paid attention to the role of the Uzbek SSR in the United Nations and other international organizations. These publications highlight both regional problems and specific countries, providing extensive factual information [7].

However, many works dedicated to the Uzbek SSR and its foreign policy relations of that time do not cover international political and cultural relations with countries whose relations with the USSR have become cold or are "not interested" in its foreign policy, including China, Japan, Indonesia, Singapore, Malaysia, South Korea, and some European countries.

This further increases the importance of a comprehensive study of the history of Uzbekistan's international relations in the field of culture. It should be noted that historians have conducted detailed research on the important role of Uzbekistan in establishing international relations with the countries of Latin America, Africa, Asia (for example, Egypt, Cuba, Chile, Pakistan, India) of the USSR [8], its role as a bridge for international political, economic, and cultural relations, and its status as an "ambassador of peace" [9].

Conclusion: The "closed policy" of the Soviet state in the external arena led to the fact that many aspects of the Uzbek SSR's international relations with foreign countries have not yet been sufficiently studied in historiography. During the Soviet period, historians covered only some aspects of the international cultural ties of the Uzbek SSR. As a result, the work dedicated to the

international relations of Uzbekistan during the Soviet period was not fully created. Today, the disclosure of many archival materials necessitates more research on this topic.

REFERENCES

1. Абдуллаев Ш.М. Вклад Узбекской ССР в экономическое, научно-техническое и культурное сотрудничество СССР с чехословацкой социалистической республикой (1959–1975 гг.): автореф. дис. на соиск. учен. степ. кандидата исторических наук: 07.00.02. – Ташкент, 1977. – 29 с.
2. Киргизбаев А.К. Научно-техническое и культурное сотрудничество Узбекистана со странами Азии в 80-е годы: автореф. дис. на соиск. учен. степ. кандидата исторических наук: 07.00.02. – Ташкент, 1991. – 29 с.
3. Туляганова Н.У. Становление и развитие движения породненных городов в Узбекистане (1961–1985 гг.): автореф. дис. на соиск. учен. степ. кандидата исторических наук: 07.00.02. – Ташкент, 1988. – стр. 2.
4. Нуриддинов Э.З. Вклад Узбекской ССР в экономическое, научно-техническое и культурное сотрудничество СССР с Венгерской Народной Республикой: 1960-1980 гг.: автореф. дис. на соиск. учен. степ. кандидата исторических наук: 07.00.02. – Ташкент, 1985. – стр. 7.
5. Сабиров А.Т. Участие Узбекской ССР в культурном сотрудничестве СССР с социалистическими странами (60-80-е гг.): автореф. дис. на соиск. учен. степ. кандидата исторических наук: 07.00.02. – Ташкент, 1987. – стр. 8.
6. Салиев У.А. Международные связи Узбекистана в исторической литературе 50-80-х годов: автореф. дис. на соиск. учен. степ. кандидата исторических наук: 07.00.02. – Андижан, 1994. – стр. 7.
7. Салиев У.А. Международные связи Узбекистана в исторической литературе 50-80-х годов: автореф. дис. на соиск. учен. степ. кандидата исторических наук: 07.00.02. – Андижан, 1994. – стр. 8.
8. Рашидова Г.Ш., Камиллов Д.А. Шараф Рашидов: портрет человека в эпохи и эпохи — в человеке. – Т.: ТАСВИР, 2017. – стр. 124.
9. Рахимов М.А. Геополитические особенности формирования внешнеполитических ведомств советских республик: на примере МИД Узбекской ССР // <https://elibrary.ru/wfqbgi>.